

ATU Research Showcase

Meet ATU's Biodiversity Champions

Understanding & Protecting our Natural Heritage in Ireland & Beyond

Ollscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh

Atlantic
Technological
University

**Research,
Innovation and
Engagement**

This booklet was compiled and designed by the ATU Research Coordinator Team, Dr James Britton, Dr Shane Conway and Dr Alan Naughton, funded through RISE@ATU.

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To mark National Biodiversity Week 2026 (15th – 24th May), a nationwide initiative putting a focus on Biodiversity and Nature, the Research Coordinator team at the Atlantic Technological University (ATU), funded through RISE@ATU, presents the fifth edition of the ATU Research Showcase Series. This edition highlights the work of ATU researchers whose work focuses on investigating and protecting biodiversity and maintaining natural habitats, on land, in oceans and fresh waters, both in Ireland and globally.

As the technological university for the West and North-West, ATU is committed to the protection and restoration of native biodiversity through research grounded in regional, national and international priorities. In alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, Ireland's National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023 – 2030 and the National Climate Action Plan 2025 (CAP25), this booklet presents a representative sample of 12 researchers whose expertise reflects interdisciplinary research and collaboration in Biodiversity and environmental stewardship across ATU.

Many other colleagues across ATU are making equally valuable contributions in both this field and other avenues of environmental stewardship and this Showcase is intended to reflect a cross-section of that collective strength rather than provide an exhaustive account.

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ATU

ATU Campus Locations

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Prof. Frances Lucy

Monitoring invasive species to protect native biodiversity

ATU Sligo

Professor Frances Lucy is a Researcher in Ecology, Director of the Centre for Environmental Research, Innovation & Sustainability (CERIS) in ATU Sligo and ATU lead for the EU GREEN European University Alliance.

Prof. Lucy is an international expert in aquatic invasive species, fisheries, water quality and sustainability. She is also President of the International Association for Open Knowledge of Invasive Alien Species (Invasivenet) which promotes understanding and policy regarding invasive species through open-source publications.

Prof. Lucy's research ranges from identifying and managing invasion of nonnative species to inform policy and prevent native biodiversity loss, citizen science and educational practices for sustainable development. She is involved in European, Shared Island and PEACEPLUS research projects, and is a Board member of the Lough's Agency.

Dr Deirdre Brophy

Understanding fish populations' response to environmental change

ATU Galway

Dr Deirdre Brophy is a Lecturer and Researcher in the Department of Natural Resources & the Environment and Strategic Leader of the Marine and Freshwater Research Centre at ATU Galway. She works with ATU colleagues and students across nationally and internationally funded research projects informing the sustainable management of fisheries and marine ecosystems.

Deirdre is an expert in fish ecology, focusing on fish growth, population connectivity, early life history processes and the environmental and ecological drivers underpinning their variability. Using growth marks and chemical constituents of fish otoliths (earstones) and scales, she determines how the fish lived, population boundaries, and how they respond to environmental change.

Deirdre and collaborators examine how fishing and climate change impacts fish distribution patterns and life histories, helping decision makers adapt to climate impacts and improving the seafood industry's resilience. Her work has furthered our understanding of population structure and migrations of species such as Atlantic bluefin tuna, providing critical information for their sustainable management.

Dr Domhnall Melly

Tourism biosecurity planning, management, and risk mitigation

ATU Sligo

Dr Domhnall Melly is a Lecturer in Tourism and Event Management at ATU Sligo, and Principal Investigator of STORYATU Sustainable Tourism and Visitor Experience Lab.

His research examines the relationship between tourism and biosecurity, centring around biodiversity conservation with particular attention to tourist mobility providing a vector for Alien Invasive Species (AIS) and disease. Dr Melly's work explores how increasing globalisation and visitor flows and tourist behaviour alters biosecurity risks in sensitive natural environments.

Central to his research is providing insights into planning and management of tourism biosecurity risk and proactive mitigation measures of visitor awareness and pro-environmental behaviour to mitigate risks to biodiversity.

Dr Melly's research contributes to discussions on nature-based tourism, biosecurity awareness, and sustainable destination management, supporting balanced tourism development with ecosystem resilience.

Dr Heather Lally

Monitoring and managing freshwater systems in agricultural catchments

ATU Galway

Dr Heather Lally, Senior Lecturer in Freshwater Ecology and Biology in the Department of Natural Resources and the Environment at ATU Galway City and Principal Investigator (P.I.) at the Marine and Freshwater Research Centre is a freshwater ecologist specialising in water chemistry monitoring, landscape mitigation measures, and restoration management. Heather is a P.I. on several projects where her research focuses on landscape management for nature restoration, and on water quality monitoring and implementation of mitigation measure to improve riverine habitats in agricultural catchments.

As P.I. of a Department of Agriculture, Food and Marine funded project, Monitoring and Evaluating Targeted Mitigation Approaches to Improve Water Quality, Heather works with farmers, advisors, agri-businesses and regional authorities to monitor rivers and using data to inform the placement and implementation of mitigation measures to improve water quality in agricultural catchments.

Dr Alina Premov

Peatland biogeochemical modelling for habitat conservation

ATU Sligo

Dr Alina Premov is an Assistant Lecturer and Principal Investigator (PI) in the Department of Environmental Science at ATU Sligo. Her research aims to better understand the dynamics of biogeochemical processes in terrestrial ecosystems using diverse modelling approaches.

Dr Premov's recent work focuses on peatland ecosystems, examining biogeochemical, hydrological and ecological interactions regulating greenhouse gas emissions, underpinning ecosystem functioning, and responses to changes in land use and management under a changing climate. While peatlands account for 3% of the world's land area, they contain approximately 33% of global soil carbon.

Dr Premov is a PI of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) funded AIMINGPEAT project using integrated modelling, measurements, and data-analysis to better understand carbon emissions in peatlands.

Dr Premov supports and informs the preservation and restoration of Irish peatlands by improving understanding of their carbon dynamics, ecosystem functioning, with implications for peatland biodiversity, helping to sustain their role as long-term carbon sinks.

Dr James Moran

Sustainable land use and agricultural systems

ATU Galway

Dr James Moran is a Senior Lecturer in Biology and Ecology at ATU Galway, where he leads the Agro-ecology & Rural Development research group. Dr Moran investigates sustainable land use and agricultural systems, emphasising agri-environmental policy and practice in integrated farming landscapes. His research spans High Nature Value farmland, biodiversity & ecosystem services, wetland systems & rural development.

Dr Moran is involved in national & international collaborations in research, innovation, operational groups and designing agri-environment schemes across Ireland and Europe. He contributes to policy with roles in the Citizens' Assembly (CA) on Biodiversity Loss, EU Young CA on Pollinators, the National Biodiversity Data Centre and on the Farming for Nature initiatives executive committee. Recently, James was part of a successful Horizon Europe proposal, where ATU is a key partner in a 26 organisation consortium developing innovative approaches to agri-environment-climate public goods. He is also Principal Investigator on the LIFE-funded RBPS_NETforNature project, building capacity & support networks for biodiversity & nature restoration across European agricultural lands.

Dr Joanne O'Brien

Bioacoustic monitoring of marine mammals

ATU Galway

Dr Joanne O'Brien is a Lecturer and Researcher in Marine Ecology and Bioacoustics in the Department of Natural Resources and the Environment at ATU Galway. She is also a Principal Investigator (PI) in the Marine and Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC) at ATU.

Dr O'Brien is an expert in monitoring marine mammal populations with bioacoustic techniques to inform conservation and model population trends. Additionally, she investigates how anthropogenic noise disturbs these animals and how to mitigate such impacts. Her work also extends to terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems, with research exploring best practices for Corncrake conservation, monitoring terrestrial soundscapes to assess habitat quality, avian biodiversity, and analysing bird populations using acoustic and ecological survey methods.

Joanne is a PI on major national and international research projects including STRAITS and MOSAIC. STRAITS supports integrated animal tracking infrastructure for marine research and conservation across Europe, while MOSAIC delivers data driven action plans and decision-making tool to enhance ocean monitoring.

Dr Christopher McEleney

Novel electrochemical sensing for habitat restoration

ATU Letterkenny

Dr Christopher McEleney is a Lecturer in Chemistry in the Department of Life & Physical Sciences at ATU Letterkenny. His research focuses on developing practical analytical methods for environmental, agricultural and food-related monitoring.

Dr McEleney has developed electrochemical methods for detecting trace metals and nutrient elements in soil extracts. His work includes developing sensors to improve analytical performance in real soil samples and developing low-cost analytical systems, including a semi-automated robotic orthophosphate analyser for analysis of soil and water samples.

More recently, Chris has taken on the role of ATU lead for PEAT+, a €19.2 million PEACEPLUS-funded cross-border project focused on peatland restoration, biodiversity and climate action. Working with partners across Northern Ireland and the border counties, PEAT+ supports large-scale peatland restoration and monitoring. Chris will contribute his expertise in analytical chemistry to monitor peatland soil health and restoration outcomes.

Dr Samantha Ball

Applied mammal ecology at the human-wildlife interface

ATU Galway

Dr Samantha Ball is a postdoctoral fellow at the Marine & Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC) in ATU Galway. Dr Bell specialises in human-wildlife conflict, focusing on applied mammal ecology in anthropogenically modified landscapes.

Samantha completed a PhD on mammal management at airfields, focusing on the Irish hare in Dublin airport. Here, she examined wildlife-aircraft strike events and developed practical, ecologically informed approaches to reduce conflict in a high-risk environment.

Samantha subsequently undertook postdoctoral research at ATU Galway, feeding into the national badger bovine tuberculosis (bTB) vaccination programme, by estimating local population densities using non-invasive genetic techniques.

Currently, Dr Bell is a researcher on the GREENBAT project, investigating the potential for bat migration in relation to offshore wind farm development. This work aims to inform sustainable renewable energy planning while minimising impacts on protected species.

Dr Emma Gray

Using phytoplankton as freshwater ecological indicators

ATU Galway

Dr Emma Gray is a Lecturer and Researcher in Freshwater Ecology in the Department of Natural Resources & the Environment at ATU Galway. Her research focusses on using phytoplankton (microscopic plants) as ecological indicators in freshwater ecosystems.

Recently her research has involved using desmids (a group of phytoplankton) as indicators of conservation status in Ireland's peatland lakes as part of an EPA funded project. Dr Gray found desmids were a reliable indicator group, and that many of the lakes sampled contained rare species.

Emma recently spent two summers in Sweden as part of an AQUACOSM-plus funded in-lake (mesocosm) experiment which included over 40 collaborators from across Europe. They investigated how projected increases in nutrient and dissolved organic matter pulses with climate change may impact lake ecosystems. During the experiment, Dr Gray led out on collecting, identifying and analysing the impact of these pulses on phytoplankton.

Dr Róisín Nash

Protecting marine biodiversity and coastal environments from plastic pollution

ATU Galway

Dr Róisín Nash is a Senior lecturer in the Department of Natural Resources & the Environment and a Principal Investigator (P.I) in the Marine and Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC) at ATU Galway.

Dr Nash's research focuses on understanding how human pressures shape marine and coastal ecosystems, with particular emphasis on biodiversity, coastal resilience, and pollution.

She leads and contributes to interdisciplinary research examining potential anthropogenic impacts, including microplastics, across marine and freshwater environments. Dr Nash is a P.I on a recently funded Interreg Atlantic Area research Project: Transforming Rivers by Reducing Aquatic Plastic Pollution (TRAP). TRAP will develop nature-based solutions in river systems to intercept plastic pollution before it reaches the sea, supporting evidence-based solutions to protect biodiversity and strengthen ecosystem resilience.

Dr Katie O'Dwyer

Exploring parasite biodiversity

ATU Galway

Dr Katie O'Dwyer is a lecturer in the Department of Natural Resources & the Environment and a Principal Investigator at the Marine and Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC) at ATU Galway.

Dr O'Dwyer is an expert in ecological parasitology. She explores parasites, a hidden and often disregarded, but vital, part of biodiversity. By studying a wide range of host and parasite groups, Katie's work reveals how rich and widespread parasite biodiversity is, across varying aquatic and terrestrial environments in Ireland and further afield.

Combining field surveys with laboratory approaches, her work uncovers previously overlooked species and examines how parasite communities respond to environmental change and interact with host ecology. It highlights that parasites are a major but often ignored component of biodiversity, playing key roles in ecosystem balance and offering valuable insights into the health and resilience of natural systems worldwide.

Marine & Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC)

Based at ATU's Galway Campus, the Marine & Freshwater Research Centre (MFRC) conducts research to support the conservation and sustainable management of marine, freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems.

MFRC researchers work closely with public sector and enterprise stakeholders to inform policy and develop innovative solutions to societal challenges.

The MFRC is host to over 45 research active staff and over 55 PhD students working on projects of regional, national and global importance.

Read more here: www.mfrc-atu.ie

Centre for Environmental Research, Innovation & Sustainability (CERIS)

The Centre for Environmental Research, Innovation and Sustainability (CERIS), based in ATU Sligo and founded in 2013, is a team of researchers (staff and students) providing key solutions in Applied Ecology, Resource Management and Past Environments.

ATU Sligo & CERIS have been conducting environmental research since the 1980's, focusing on solutions for the management of land, water, natural resources and for the development of alternative energy technologies.

Read more here: www.atu.ie/research/research-centres/ceris

ATU Mountbellew

In March 2025, Mountbellew Agricultural College (MAC) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU) signed a Memorandum of Understanding to deepen academic collaboration and expand research and educational opportunities in the agricultural and environmental sectors.

Under this agreement, MAC and ATU are working together across a range of initiatives, including the delivery of undergraduate and postgraduate programmes, shared access to academic resources, collaborative research and innovation projects, and strengthened links with industry and student placement opportunities.

With over 120 hectares of farmland encompassing tillage, dairy and sheep enterprises, alongside modern farm infrastructure and equipment, MAC provides a unique real-world “living laboratory” for applied agricultural, environmental and biodiversity research within ATU.

Current research activity at MAC spans areas such as biodiversity monitoring using drone-based technologies, climate-resilient crop and protein production, and the application of biochar and other innovations to improve soil health and reduce emissions. Through these initiatives, MAC is delivering impactful, practice-based research in partnership with ATU and a range of academic and industry collaborators.

ATU Green Campus

The An Taisce Green Campus program founded in 2007, encourages third level campus communities to engage in environmental education, management and action to enhance sustainability on campus.

In 2011, ATU's Mayo campus became the first Institute of Technology campus to be awarded the Green Campus status. The Mayo campus currently has Green flags for Biodiversity, Energy, Waste, Transport, Water & Climate Change. The Mayo Green campus committee, chaired by Dr Deirdre Garvey, consists of students & staff voluntarily monitoring all flag areas & projects.

The ATU Mayo Green campus projects include the natural regeneration of meadows through different mowing regimes, constructing a campus pond habitat and the Save Our Swifts Project. Read more here:

<https://www.atu.ie/connect/projects-and-programmes/green-campus-mayo>

ATU Sligo is a proud member of the Green Campus network, currently holding Green Flags for Litter & Waste, Energy and Biodiversity. This initiative is led by a student committee, supported by staff and campus management.

The committee is now working towards the Green Flag for Sustainable Travel. This is supported by collaboration across teaching and learning, research, campus operations, the ATU community and wider stakeholders. Read more here:

<https://www.atu.ie/connect/projects-and-programmes/green-campus-sligo>

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